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Cellulolytic Potentials of Fungal Isolates from Sawdust Environments

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ABSTRACT

Environmental wastes from agricultural activities are natural sources of bio-tools, particularly fungi of industrial importance for the synthesis of lignocellulytic enzymes. The aim of the study is to evaluate the cellulolytic potential of fungal isolates from sawdust environment. Sawdust samples were collected from sawmills and transported to the laboratory for processing. Fungal isolation and characterization, screening for Cellulase production, Fermentation Process for Cellulase Activity, and Screening of Cellulolytic Enzyme Activity were done using the zone of hydrolysis technique. A total of four cellulolytic isolates (*Aspergillus carbonarius*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*) was confirmed. All the isolates demonstrated cellulase production ability in the sawdust higher than the CMC, with *Aspergillus carbonarius* having the highest activity at 25 °C (35.00 mm) and 35 °C (39.00 mm) on sawdust than the CMC (30.00 mm) respectively. Furthermore, the cellulase production activity at 35 °C was higher than 25 °C. Sawdust is an excellent habitat for fungi that produce cellulase specifically at 25 °C. Thus, following more research, the acquired fungal species can be used to produce cellulase industrially.

Keywords: Cellulolytic, fungi, sawdust environment

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental wastes from agricultural activities are natural sources of bio-tools, particularly fungi of industrial importance for the synthesis of lignocellulytic enzymes, in

addition to being the primary cause of pollution in the environment. The most abundant renewable material produced on Earth, agricultural practices and agro-allied businesses like breweries, paper and pulp, textile, and lumber sectors all contribute to the accumulation of agro-waste (Cyrus & Juwon, 2019). Waste such as sawdust, which is made of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin and comes from plant sources called lignocellulose. Because of its large molecular weight and the presence of physiologically durable carbon-to-carbon ether bonds, lignin is well known for its resistance to microbial destruction (Ojo-Omoniyi *et al.*, 2021).

Making up about 33% of all plant matter, cellulose is the most prevalent organic substance on earth and a complex carbohydrate. Plants, algae, and some bacteria use cellulose as a structural component to give their cell walls strength and rigidity. It is a valuable source of dietary fiber for both humans and animals, but only a particular class of microorganisms possesses the enzymes necessary to decompose it and use it as a source of energy. Cellulose has several industrial applications, such as the production of paper, bioethanol, and medications (Lokhande *et al.*, 2023). Cellulose is a significant part of plant biomass and is crucial to the recycling of organic materials in the environment. Microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi play a major role in the breakdown of cellulose in soil and water, releasing nutrients back into the ecosystem.

Cellulases are produced by a wide range of microorganisms, including filamentous fungi, bacteria, yeasts, and actinobacteria. Although many different types of fungi can break down cellulose as a carbon source, the genera *Clostridium*, *Cellulomonas*, *Thermomonospora*, *Trichoderma*, and *Aspergillus* are the most commonly used as cellulolytic agents because of their ability to produce cellulases with high enzymatic activity (Darwesh *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, it has been established that a variety of microorganisms, including actinomycetes (*Thermomonospora fusca*), mesophilic anaerobic fungi (*Neocallimastix frontalis*, *Piromonas communis*) and thermophilic aerobic fungi (*Sporotrichum thermophile*, *Thermoascus aurantiacus*, *Humicola insolens*) have been shown to produce active cellulases (Sulman & Rehman, 2023).

Solid trash is constituted of 40-50% cellulose, 9-12% hemicelluloses, and 10-15% lignin on a dry weight basis. In the current technoeconomic period, the energy and environmental crises arose due to the enormous volume of cellulosic materials are dumped as "waste" (Gautam *et al.*, 2012). The improper disposal of this trash has a negative effect on human health and the environment as a whole. Under ambient conditions, microorganisms carry out their metabolic operations quickly and remarkably selectively, thanks to a variety of enzyme-mediated reactions. The search for enzymes in natural microbial biodiversity has been intense due to the need for an enzyme substitute for harsh chemical technology. Under the right circumstances, a diverse range of microorganisms can create a number of enzymes, including cellulase. Therefore, finding proof of lignocellulose breakdown by fungal isolates living in a sawdust environment was the goal of this study.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2. 1. Sample Collection

Sawdust samples was collected from sawmills into a sample bag, labelled and transported to the laboratory for processing. The collected sample, weighing 100g, underwent pretreatment

through sun drying and subsequent oven drying at 80 °C for 1 hour, followed by cooling. Post-pretreatment, the sawdust was blended to achieve a finer consistency and then filtered using a 0.1 mm mesh sieve. The filtered product was stored in an airtight polythene bag at room temperature until needed.

2. 2. Isolation and Characterization of Fungi

The samples were placed in sterile sample bottles. Subsequently, serial dilutions were prepared, with dilution factors of 10^{-3} and 10^{-5} . Inoculation was performed on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) supplemented with 0.001 mg/L of chloramphenicol. The inoculated agar plates were then incubated at a temperature of 28 ± 2 °C for a duration of 5 days. Following incubation, colonies obtained from the cultures were sub-cultured to achieve pure cultures. Maintenance of stock cultures involved PDA slants kept at 28 °C. Identification of the isolates was carried out through examination of phenotypic characteristics, including colony color and growth patterns. Additionally, microscopic features were utilized in the identification process (Umoren *et al.*, 2025).

2. 3. Screening for Cellulase Producing Fungi

The experiment involved spot inoculating plates with spore suspensions of pure fungal cultures. These cultures were placed on minimal salt medium containing specific components, such as 1g of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) agar, 0.25g of NaNO_3 , 0.1g of KH_2PO_4 , 0.05g of MgSO_4 , 0.06g of CaCl_2 , 1.5g of agar agar powder, and 0.001g of chloramphenicol dissolved in 100 ml of H_2O . The goal was to induce the secretion of cellulase. The plates were then incubated at a temperature of 28 ± 2 °C for 5 days. Additionally, other plates were similarly prepared with minor modifications. The spore suspensions were inoculated onto minimal salt medium containing 1g of cassava peel, along with the other specified components. Once again, the plates were incubated at 28 ± 2 °C for three days to promote cellulase secretion (Sivakumaran, 2014; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021).

Following the incubation period, the plates underwent a staining process. They were flooded with a 1% Congo red solution for 15 minutes and subsequently de-stained using a 1M NaCl solution for 10 minutes. The outcome of interest was the diameter of the zone of clearance surrounding each fungal colony, which was then measured. Based on the results, the fungal isolates exhibiting the highest zone of clearance were selected for further cellulase production (Reddy *et al.*, 2014; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021).

2. 4. Fermentation Process for Cellulase Activity of the Fungal Isolate

The fermentation process involved assessing the growth of fungal isolates under varying incubation temperatures. Specifically, the fungal isolates were cultivated at 25 °C and 35 °C to determine their optimal growth conditions and the temperature resulting in the greatest zone of inhibition (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021).

2. 5. Screening of Cellulolytic Enzyme Activity

Microorganisms that produce cellulose were screened using agar plates enriched with carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) as the control carbon source, and on separate plates containing cassava peel as the sole carbon source. These plates were then incubated at 28 ± 2 °C for a specific number of days. The screening process was based on the interaction between cellulose

and congo red dye. The congo red dye bound to integral cellulose, creating red zones, while areas with cellulose that had been enzymatically hydrolyzed displayed clear zones (Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). The size of these clear zones was measured to calculate the enzymatic activity index.

$$\text{Enzymatic activity (EA)} = \frac{\text{Diameter of Clear Zone}}{\text{Diameter of Inoculum (Colony)}}$$

2. 6. Analysis of data

Data collected were presented in table and charts using Microsoft Excel 2023 .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Results

The fermentative activities of Cellulolytic Organisms on Saw dust against CMC at 25 °C is presented in Table 1, it revealed four cellulolytic organisms (*Aspergillus carbonarius*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*). *Aspergillus carbonarius* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (35.00 mm) than the CMC (30.00 mm), *Trichoderma harzianum* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (31.00 mm) than the CMC (21.00 mm), *Aspergillus niger* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (30.00 mm) than the CMC (25.00 mm) while *Aspergillus flavus* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (30.00 mm) than the CMC (19.00 mm).

Table 1. Fermentative Activities of Cellulolytic Organisms on Sawdust against CMC at 25 °C.

Fungal Isolate	Saw dust (mm)	CMC (mm)
<i>Aspergillus carbonarius</i>	35.00	30.00
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	31.00	21.00
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	30.00	25.00
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	30.00	19.00

The fermentative activities of Cellulolytic Organisms on Saw dust against CMC at 35 °C is presented in Table 2, it showed that *A. carbonarius* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (39.00 mm) than the CMC (30.00 mm), *T. harzianum* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (20.00 mm) than the CMC (11.00 mm), *A. niger* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (27.00 mm) than the CMC (19.00 mm) while *A. flavus* showed higher fermentative activities on saw dust (28.00 mm) than the CMC (20.00 mm).

The comparative analysis of the enzymes activities of the fungal isolates at 25 °C and 35 °C is presented in Figure 1, it showed that *A. carbonarius* showed higher enzymatic activities on saw dust (4.20; 3.20 mm) than the CMC (3.40; 2.90 mm) at 25 °C and 35 °C respectively.

T. harzianum showed higher enzymatic activities on saw dust (3.80; 2.20 mm) than the CMC (3.30; 1.60 mm) at 25 °C and 35 °C respectively. *A. niger* showed higher enzymatic activities on saw dust (4.10; 3.60 mm) than the CMC (3.70; 3.10 mm) at 25 °C and 35 °C respectively while *A. flavus* showed higher enzymatic activities on saw dust (4.50; 3.80 mm) than the CMC (3.90; 3.20 mm) at 25 °C and 35 °C respectively

Table 2. Fermentative Activities of Cellulolytic Organisms on Saw dust against CMC at 35 °C.

Fungal Isolate	Saw dust (mm)	CMC (mm)
<i>Aspergillus carbonarius</i>	39.00	30.00
<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	20.00	11.00
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	27.00	19.00
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	28.00	20.00

Figure 1. Comparative Enzymatic Activities of Fungal Isolates at 25 °C and 35 °C.

3. 2. Discussion

The desire to isolate and identify microorganisms that are overproducers and/or that develop innovative exoenzymes that could break down organic wastes much more quickly has motivated one of the main approaches to biotechnological research into agrowastes. Their resilience to unfavorable conditions in the planned industrial or environmental applications is another (Howard *et al.*, 2023). The microorganisms ought to have every quality needed to carry out these magnificent duties in an economical manner (Lynd *et al.*, 2002).

Different settings are being searched for possible candidate microorganisms with the needed features in order to accomplish this goal. According to Damisa *et al.* (2023), the isolated habitat significantly impacts the fermentation-related performance of microorganisms. It is also assumed that the qualities and physicochemical features of the microorganism's surroundings are reflected in the characteristics of a specific microbial enzyme. Sawdust was observed in this investigation to be a fungal biotool with distinctive novelties in cellulase zymosynthesis. It has been documented that microbes for the synthesis of enzymes can be isolated from a variety of studies, including those involving agro-wastes (Olaniyi *et al.*, 2019), decomposing organic soil (Nadeem *et al.*, 2017), and abattoir waste (Narasimha *et al.*, 2018).

Based on the clear zones that developed on carboxymethyl cellulose agar plates, isolates were screened for cellulytic characteristics. The ability of the isolates to produce extracellular cellulase was indicated by the formation of distinct zones on agar plates containing carboxymethyl cellulose. On carboxymethyl cellulose agar plates, fungi isolated from various agricultural wastes and sawmill dirt revealed varying activity ratios. This implied that the isolates' capacities to produce cellulose varied. The ability of the cellulose produced by the isolates to diffuse through the medium and/or the direct functionality of their genetic composition to secrete cellulase with high diffusion speed could be the cause of the variations in width of the clear zones that the isolates formed (Akinyele *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, it is known that the fungi secrete a wide variety of extracellular enzymes into their growth media, such as hemicellulases, cellulases, pectinases, chitinases, amylases, proteases, phytases, and mannases (Sanjogita *et al.*, 2024).

According to the investigation, there were more enzymatic activities from the isolate in the sawdust compared to the carboxymethyl cellulose and more suitable temperature at 25 °C compare to 35 °C, this is likely because there were more substrates available for fungal growth. This supports the finding of Sánchez (2019), which states that lignocellulosic substrates, like sawdust, are suitable substrates for fungi and come in a variety of forms. These substrates are made of natural biopolymers including cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The high enzymatic activity of the fungus may be responsible for their ability to create a range of extracellular enzymes needed for depolymerizing various refractory polysaccharide biomass in sawdust.

A possible explanation for the decreased enzymatic activity in CMC could be the amount of nutrients available for fungal development. In addition, the isolates can be considered transitory microorganisms that exist only in the lack of inhibiting agents (Arotupin, 2017).

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4. 1. Conclusion

Sawdust provides an exceptional habitat for various fungal species, creating an ideal environment that fosters their growth and proliferation. When maintained at a warm

temperature of approximately 25 °C, this substrate becomes particularly conducive to the flourishing of these fungi. In such conditions, the fungi not only thrive but also engage in the production of cellulase, a crucial enzyme responsible for the breakdown of cellulose. This enzymatic activity is vital for processes such as biomass degradation, which can significantly enhance efficiency in industries that rely on cellulose-rich materials.

4. 2. Recommendations

It is recommended that, by delving deeper into the characteristics and capabilities of these unique fungal species, we have the potential to harness their cellulase production. This could lead to innovative industrial applications, paving the way for advancements in processes like waste recycling, biofuel production, and the development of sustainable materials, ultimately driving greater efficiency and innovation across multiple sectors.

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